

Appendix: Estimating Costs of Open Access Publishing

NWO and ZonMw Open Access Monitor 2023

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Table of contents

Estimating costs of open access publishing

4

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The costs associated with open access publishing research funded by NWO and ZonMw is largely unknown.

NWO allows its grant money to be used only to pay for publication fees for full OA journals registered in DOAJ. For that purpose, NWO grants include a budget of € 15K per fte per year for material costs, from which APCs can be paid. ZonMw grants include a dedicated budget for open access costs of € 5K per project, which can similarly be used to pay APCs for full OA journals only. Since there is no detailed accounting on project level required, it is unknown to which extent these budgets are being spent on open access publication costs.

Publications in hybrid OA journals are not eligible for NWO and ZonMw funding but are in many cases financially covered by the transformative agreements negotiated by the Universities of the Netherlands and Dutch research libraries network (UNL/UKB). Although details about these contracts are publicly available on the ESAC-registry¹, the way the costs of these agreements are structured is often opaque. For most contracts it is not clear how much is paid for the publishing part and how much for reading the content. As mentioned before, what lacks is article-level data on which publications are covered by the agreements and which are not. This also makes it hard to determine the costs associated with the publishing of NWO and ZonMw funded research covered by these agreements.

In a recent study commissioned by the French Open Science programme a novel method was used to estimate the costs associated with OA publishing using openly available data from the OpenAPC project.² We have replicated this method with our own dataset. By using the publicly available API of OpenAPC we have been able to collect the average APC price (if applicable) for 84% of the publications in our dataset. Table x presents an overview of the aggregated (potential) costs per OA-type for all articles published in 2023 and for those articles with a corresponding author affiliated with a Dutch institution.

Corresponding authorship is an important variable to take into account when looking at open access publishing costs because often it determines ‘who pays’ for the publication fee.³ In case of transformative agreements corresponding authorship determines whether a given publication is covered by an agreement and thus the publication fee is funded by the institution which has subscribed to the contract. In case of full gold OA for which APCs are payable it is often assumed that the corresponding author pays for the APC (from their grant money or institutional budget). However, NWO does not require corresponding authorship for its grant money to be used for payment of APC’s for full OA journals. In principle, all full OA publications which acknowledge NWO funding are eligible for reimbursement of publication costs.

¹ <https://esac-initiative.org/about/transformative-agreements/agreement-registry/>

² Antoine Blanchard, Diane Thierry, Maurits van der Graaf. Retrospective and prospective study of the evolution of APC costs and electronic subscriptions for French institutions. Comité pour la science ouverte. 2022. <https://dx.doi.org/10.52949/26>

³ Bruns, A., Rimmert, C., & Taubert, N. (2020). Who Pays? Comparing Cost Sharing Models for a Gold Open Access Publication Environment. *Journal of Library Administration*, 60(8), 853–874. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2020.1820275>

OA types	n (all)		costs (all)	n (corresp)	costs (corresp)
Diamond OA	131		€ 98.250	44	€ 33.000
Full Gold	1.922		€ 3.445.526	1.132	€ 1.928.526
Hybrid in TA	1.979		€ 4.224.126	1.979	€ 4.224.126
Hybrid out of TA	1.463		€ 3.176.215	200	€ 469.507
Green	562		€ 1.216.151	140	€ 298.072
Closed	553		€ 858.769	137	€ 251.505
Total	6.610		€ 13.019.038	3.632	€ 7.204.737

Table 1: Number and estimated (potential) costs of NWO/ZonMw funded publications in 2023 according to OA-type using OpenAPC as a source. Yellow highlighted are the costs that are eligible for NWO/ZonMw project funding.

The following conclusions can be drawn:

- In 2023 a total of 1.922 articles were published in full OA journals for which an estimated € 3.4m euro was paid. Potentially this entire sum was paid for from NWO/ZonMw funding because in NWO and ZonMw's policy the option is left open for claiming OA costs for publication in full OA journals irrespective of whether the grantee is corresponding author on the publication or not. Taking into account corresponding authorship, 1.132 articles were published for which € 1.9m was paid.
- In 2023 a total of 1.979 articles were published as part of a transformative agreement by corresponding authors affiliated with one of the Dutch institutions. Based on the data of OpenAPC it is estimated that the library consortium UKB and institutions have paid € 4.2m for these publications. A further 1.463 articles associated with NWO funding were published in journals not covered by TA's amounting to another € 3.1m euro to be paid for APC's. Only 200 of these were authored by researchers affiliated with Dutch institutions in journals for which apparently no deal was in place, resulting in a cost of € 469k outside of existing deals and would neither be refunded by NWO. As stated above these figures should be considered very rough estimates and used with much caution as the 'real' costs of OA publishing under these agreements is not known.
- 563 (and 137) articles were made open access using the green route, for which no payments were required. If the authors would have chosen to pay APC's for these publications (if possible) that would have cost €1,2m or € 298k for corresponding authors.
- 553 articles were published closed access. Would the authors have chosen to publish OA (where possible) that would have € 858k or € 251k.
- For diamond OA the situation is more complex. While no direct costs are incurred for publication in these journals, the journals do require financial support. NWO already supports a number of diamond OA initiatives, such as Openjournals.nl, SciPost and the Open Library for the Humanities. Additionally the SCOAP3 initiative is supported through NWO's Nikhef institute. Although under the diamond model, there is usually no reimbursement on a per item basis, here we assume a per item price/contribution of € 750 euros which would amount to € 90k in direct financial support.

In total it is estimated that a sum of € 10.9m was paid in 2023 to make NWO funded research open access. € 3.4m of this was potentially paid directly by NWO funding. € 4.6m was funded by the Dutch institutions, mostly through the transformative agreements negotiated by UNL/UKB.

Figure 1 provides a breakdown of the estimated aggregate costs paid in 2023 for publications in full gold and hybrid journals (by corresponding authors affiliated with institutions in the Netherlands) for the top 15 publishers (representing 95% of total costs for publications in full gold and hybrid journals by corresponding authors affiliated with institutions in the Netherlands). A distinction is made between costs falling within and outside of the transformative agreements that are in place.

Open access costs top 15 publishers for gold and hybrid OA

Figure 1. Breakdown of the estimated publications cost for full gold and hybrid OA publications funded by NWO/ZonMw published in 2023 (by corresponding authors affiliated with Dutch institutions) with the top 15 publishers within and outside of the existing transformative agreements (TA) in place in the Netherlands.

It can be concluded that the transformative agreements in the Netherlands cover important parts of the NWO funded research output. Still, however, a substantial amount of € 1.8m was paid to the top 15 publishers to allow for the publication of articles in full gold or hybrid journals **outside of these contracts**. To a large degree this sum can be accounted for by publications in full gold open access journals which are usually left out of the transformative agreements negotiated by the UKB/UNL. The contract with Elsevier being a notable exception.

The source of funding for these so-called “APCs in the wild” can be NWO (from grant money) and ZonMw (dedicated OA budget) in case of full OA articles or other (institutional) budgets available to the authors. It must be noted that these payments are not under the cost control which is considered to emanate from national publisher contracts negotiated by UNL/UKB. Of specific concern is the contract with Springer Nature. The above figures indicate that in case of NWO-funded research substantially more money is flowing to this publisher uncontrolled outside of the agreement, then under the agreement. This is clearly the result of the large number of full OA journals in the Springer/Nature portfolio which are not included in the national deal.

Important to note are also the four full gold OA publishers: Frontiers, MDPI, PLOS and BMJ. According to the estimates presented here, these publishers have been paid € 628k in 2023 to publish NWO/ZonMw funded research open access. But again, this happened without an overarching contract that would allow negotiations with the publisher about cost- and quality control.

In conclusion, we would like to emphasize again that the cost estimates presented here should be considered as very rough estimates and that the data on which these calculations are based have important limitations. In the absence of publicly available information, in our opinion it is nevertheless a valid way to map the costs of OA publishing of NWO funded research based on open sources. In future editions of this monitor, we plan to further enrich and validate this method. To make metadata about costs even more complete and accurate, we hope that more institutions will provide their APC-data to open sources, such as OpenAPC in the near future.

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